

drug-herb interactions. Arch Intern Med, 158 (1998), pp. 2200-2211

6. Adome RO, Gachihi JW, Onegi B, Tamale J, Apio SO. The cardiotoxic effect of the crude ethanolic extract of Nerium oleander in the isolated guinea pig hearts. Afr Health Sci. 2003 Aug;3(2):77-82. PMID: 12913798; PMCID: PMC2141602.

7. Orhan IE, Gokbulut A, Senol FS. Adonis sp., Convallaria sp., Strophanthus sp., Thevetia sp., and Leonurus sp. - Cardiotoxic Plants with Known Traditional Use and a Few Preclinical and Clinical Studies. Curr Pharm Des. 2017;23(7):1051-1059. doi: 10.2174/1381612822666161010104548. PMID: 27748195.

8. O. S. Kukhtenko, L. S. Simonyan, Ye. V. Hladukh Market research of medicinal products which are used in cardiological diseases treatment. Current issues in pharmacy and medicine: science and practice 2017; 10 (2), 219–223. UDC: 614.272:615.22:616.12-009. DOI: 10.14739/2409-2932.2017.2.103783

9. Oberoi L, Akiyama T, Lee KH, Liu SJ. The aqueous extract, not organic extracts, of Terminalia arjuna bark exerts cardiotoxic effect on adult ventricular myocytes. Phytomedicine. 2011 Feb 15;18(4):259-65. doi: 10.1016/j.phymed.2010.07.006. PMID: 21315570.

NEPHROPROTECTORS WITH PLANT ORIGIN

Ratsa V.,

*Assistant Department of Internal Medicine
Bukovinian State Medical University, Chernivtsi*

Holodniak Yu.,

4th-year student of the 11th group at the BSMU in Chernivtsi, Ukraine

Navrotska D.

4th-year student of the 11th group at the BSMU in Chernivtsi, Ukraine

Cheipesh M.

4th-year student of the 11th group at the BSMU in Chernivtsi, Ukraine

Abstract

In this research, we want to reveal the issue of nephroprotectors with plant origin and their importance in treatment of acute kidney injury. It is known that acute kidney injury (AKI) can occur in nearly 20–200 per million population in the community. It is important to know that AKI is associated with morbidity and mortality; every year almost 2 million people worldwide die of AKI, whereas AKI survivors are at high risk of developing chronic kidney disease (CKD) and end-stage renal disease (ESRD) — conditions that carry a high burden. By the way, many plants have been well recognized for their nephroprotective properties. Moreover, they have a wide range of pharmacological effects, the most significant of which are antioxidant, antihypoxic, angioprotective, membrane-stabilizing and anti-inflammatory, that can help in solving this issue.

Keywords: acute kidney injury, nephroprotectors, flavonoids, drugs with plant origin, antioxidants.

Introduction

It is important to note that researchers say that by 2040, kidney disease could become the fifth leading cause of death among all diseases in the world. Kidney damage can be caused by some pre-, intra- and postrenal factors. Diabetes, liver diseases, rhabdomyolysis, and intestinal microbiota are among the prerenal factors. Regarding postrenal factors, such diseases as lithiasis or blood clots in the ureters, prostate cancer, urethral obstruction, prostate enlargement and urinary tract infections can be distinguished. Also, it is important do not forget about the nephrotoxicity of drugs, they can also cause severe kidney damage. As well, there is such a thing as the nephrotoxicity of drugs, they can also cause severe kidney damage. Therefore, it should be noted that we must supplement the treatment with drugs that protect the kidneys, namely nephroprotectors [1].

Materials and methods.

Various scientific materials were used during the execution of this work, namely articles by modern researchers, which fully cover this topic.

The research was carried out in various services, namely PubMed, Cochrane, The Lancet, etc.

Research results

Over the last decades, a lot of research has been carried out, which allows us to learn more about acute kidney injury, as well as to improve diagnosis in the early stages. Consensus definitions were therefore created in 2012 and finally unified by the Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) group [2].

Treatment standards are constantly changing to influence patient survival; but even so, mortality in severe APF remains very high despite several improvements in treatment.

In order to better understand the importance of nephroprotectors, it is important to understand why some drugs are nephrotoxic. For example, consider such a drug as Gentamicin.

Gentamicin, a strong cationic drug which precipitates acute nephrotoxicity, because of accumulation at biological membranes and causes net increase in oxidative stress and lipid peroxidation leading to necrotic changes in renal tubules [3].

There are studies where described that there are several phytoconstituents and plants extracts demonstrated significant anti-oxidant and cyto-protective activities. Vitex negundo Linn. (VN), Oroxyllum indicum

Vent. (OI) and *Barringtonia acutangula* Linn. (BA) are widely found throughout the Asian sub-continent [3].

As a result, were made conclusions that the extracts of VN, OI and BA significantly attenuate the nephrotoxicity by elevation of body weight, superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT) and glutathione peroxidase (GPx) or lowering urine lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) and creatinine, serum urea; serum creatinine and lipid peroxidation (LPO) respectively [3].

In some works, data on medicinal plants of the world flora, which have nephroprotective properties, have been analyzed. The researchers summarized the information about the biologically active substances of these plants and about the mechanisms of their action at different levels. Also, after analyzing several works, we understood the prospects for further research and the possibilities of using phytopreparations in kidney diseases [4].

The concept of nephroprotection involves primary prevention of painful diseases, as well as slowing down the process of their progression [6]. Nephroprotectors are aimed at reducing the effects of nephrotoxic factors,

including drugs and adverse environmental effects. An integral protective effect on the kidneys by a complex mechanism is inherent in a number of drugs [5].

Nephroprotective activity is an integral protective effect on the kidneys, which allows to slow down the rate of progression of nephropathies to terminal chronic kidney disease (CKD), or to reduce the effect of nephrotoxic factors. It can be implemented in many ways [7]. The targets of certain nephrotropic biologically active compounds (BAC) are the fundamental mechanisms of cell damage - hypoxia and its consequences, disruption of membrane transport, apoptosis and lipid peroxidation (LPO).

Nowadays, thanks to advances in research, therapeutic effects can be demonstrated using validated in vitro or in vivo models and even clinical trials. They aimed to confirm the benefits of plants and derivatives, discarding plants that have false or placebo effects. The main idea of using this group of drugs is to recommend the use of plant origin drugs, which are less toxic than synthetic drugs [1].

Table 1

Plant nephroprotectors with polytropic organoprotective effect [7]

Biologically active compounds	
<i>Phenolic compounds</i>	
Derivatives of hydroxycinnamic acids	acteoside lithospermic acid B magnesium lithospermat B salvianolic acid B
Derivatives of chromene	methylripariochromene A
Flavonoids	artnonin E, licochalcone A astragalin butein hesperidin hyperoside catechin quercetin kaempferol, fisetin luteolin morin, morin hydrate naringin, naringenin robinin cinnaroside
Diarylheptanones	curcumin
Flavolignans	silybin silibinin silicristine
Stilbens	resveratrol
Anthracene derivatives	emodin emodin-1-O- β -D-glucoside physceon physceon-1-O- β -D-glucoside
Lignins	nordihydroguaretic acid
Tannins	procyanidin-B-2 3,3'-di-O-gallate RG-tannin
Ellagic acid, epigallocatechin gallate (-) epicatechin-3-O-gallate	
Secoisolarresinol diglucoside	
<i>Triterpene saponins</i>	
Alisol A, Alisol B	
Betulin	
Ginsenoside-Rd, Ginsenoside Rg1, Ginsenoside Rb1	
Glycerin-3-monodesmoside	

Glycyrrhizin
Lupeol
Oleanolic and ursolic acids
Prothophanaxdiol, prothophanaxtriol
Saikosaponin-a, saikosaponin-d
<i>Terpene lactones</i>
Bilobalide
<i>Phytoecdysteroids</i>
Ecdysterone, turkesterone
<i>Carotenoids</i>
Astaxanthin
Crocin
Lycopene
<i>Alkaloids</i>
Berberine
Greenlandicin, epiberberine, magnoflorine, palmatine
Coptisine
Phelodendrin
Chelerythrine
Amides
Capsaicin
<i>Amino acid derivatives</i>
S-allylcysteine (SAC)
<i>Peptides</i>
Gly-Arg-γ-Glu-Val-NH ₂
<i>Other substances</i>
Astragalosides
Diallyl disulfide
Cryptotanshinone
Ligustrazine
Sodium L-malate
Thymoquinone

Table 1 lists biologically active substances that have nephroprotective properties. The effect of nephroprotective herbal BARs can be directed nitroxidergic mechanisms, renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS), renal hemodynamics, metabolites of arachidonic acid and other mediators of inflammation, steroid hormones. BAC medicinal plants (MP) can normalize nitrogen and lipid metabolism [8, 9], exert an antihypertensive effect, including caused by renal effects [7, 10, 11].

The most popular herbal nephroprotector in Ukraine is Nephrofit, which is available in two forms: herbal and tablet. "Nephrofit-Tab", which, respectively, is in tablet form of 0.85 g No. 60 (10x6). "Nephrofit-Tab" consists of 9 medicinal plants with high biological activity, the action of which is aimed at achieving a diuretic effect, increasing the nitrogen-excreting function of the kidneys: Herba Equiseti arven-sis, Sambucus nigra L., Herba Polygoni avicularis, Matricariae flores, Herba Melilotus officinalis, Herba Bidens tripartita, Arctostaphylos uva-ursi L., Folia menthae piperitae, Fructus Anethi graveolentis. They have a positive effect on the depurative function of the kidneys.

The complex of biologically active substances (glycoside - arbutin, flavonoids, phenolic acids, coumarins and others) contained in these plants have a beneficial effect on kidney function.

Medicinal plants in "Nephrofit-Tab" have diuretic, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial properties. The components of the herbal preparation contain: vitamins/provitamins: E, C, B3, B4, P, carotene, macro- and micro-elements: Ca, Mg, K, Fe, Mn, Cu, Zn, Mo, Se, B, Co, Cr, Al, Ba, Ni.

It is recommended to be used as a source of biologically active substances, helps to improve the functioning of the kidneys and genitourinary system, has a mild diuretic property.

It is also recommended as an anti-inflammatory, antispasmodic and antibacterial agent for the prevention and complex therapy of inflammatory diseases of the kidneys and urinary tract, which are accompanied by a decrease in urinary and nitrogen-excreting function, urolithiasis, cystitis, diseases of the pelvic organs.

Conclusion

Kidney disease can be caused by several factors or diseases classified as pre-renal, intrinsic and post-renal through which they lead to kidney damage. Methods of treating kidney diseases in most cases cause side effects and lead to nephrotoxicity. Therefore, it is suggested to use plant components and their biologically active molecules, which have a nephroprotective effect, acting as antioxidants, anti-inflammatory, antiseptic and diuretic effects. The reviewed studies describe the positive use of plants and their bioactive molecules to mitigate drug-induced kidney damage. In addition, this review pro-

vides a better understanding of how plants act as molecular modulators to alleviate prerenal and postrenal disorders that may indirectly or subsequently lead to the development of chronic kidney disease.

References

1. Tienda-Vázquez MA, Morreeuw ZP, Sosa-Hernández JE, Cardador-Martínez A, Sabath E, Melchor-Martínez EM, Iqbal HMN, Parra-Saldivar R. Nephroprotective Plants: A Review on the Use in Pre-Renal and Post-Renal Diseases. *Plants (Basel)*. 2022 Mar 18;11(6):818. doi: 10.3390/plants11060818. PMID: 35336700; PMCID: PMC8955229.
2. Matuszkiewicz-Rowińska J, Małyszko J. Acute kidney injury, its definition, and treatment in adults: guidelines and reality. *Pol Arch Intern Med*. 2020 Dec 22;130(12):1074-1080. doi: 10.20452/pamw.15373. Epub 2020 May 19. PMID: 32426960.
3. Mishra S, Pani SR, Sahoo S. Anti-nephrotoxic activity of some medicinal plants from tribal rich pockets of Odisha. *Pharmacognosy Res*. 2014 Jul;6(3):210-7. doi: 10.4103/0974-8490.132598. PMID: 25002801; PMCID: PMC4080501.
4. O.V. Tovchiga, S. Yu. Shtrygol THE NEPHROPROTECTIVE PROPERTIES OF THE BIOLOGICALLY ACTIVE SUBSTANCES AND HERBAL PREPARATIONS, January 2010.
5. O. V. Tovchyga, S. M. Rolik, S. Yu. Shtrygol DRUGS WITH NEPHROPROTECTIVE EFFECT: OVERVIEW OF THE UKRAINIAN PHARMACEUTICAL MARKET, UKRAINIAN BIOPHARMACEUTICAL JOURNAL, No. 2 (13) 2011, UDC 612.460:615-015.
6. Shestakova M.V. Nephroprotection: the role of blood pressure in the progression of kidney pathology / M.V. Shestakova // *Therapeutic archive*. – 2001.– No. 6.– P. 64-6.
7. THE NEPHROPROTECTIVE PROPERTIES OF THE BIOLOGICALLY ACTIVE SUBSTANCES AND HERBAL PREPARATIONS. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259621872_THE_NEPHROPROTECTIVE_PROPERTIES_OF_THE_BIOLOGICALLY_ACTIVE_SUBSTANCES_AND_HERBAL_PREPARATIONS [accessed May 08 2023].
8. Vasylychenko E.A. Phytopreparations for nephrology: raz-8.raboty GNCLS and modern aspects of pharmacotherapy of diseased kidneys / E.A. Vasylychenko // *Pharmacom*. -1999. – No. 3-4. - P. 78-86.
9. Dudar I.A. Herbal preparation Khofitol in treatment of 9. patients with kidney diseases / I.A. Piper // *Doc-tor*. - 2001. - No. 6. - P. 54-56.
10. Effects of chronic quercetin treatment in experimental renovascular hypertension / M.F. Garcia-Saura, M. Galisteo, C. Villar et al. // *Mol. Cell. Biochem*. – 2005. – Vol. 270, No 1-2. – P. 147-155.
11. Antihypertensive actions of methylripariochromene A from *Orthosiphon aristatus*, an Indonesian traditional medicinal plant / T. Matsubara, T. Bohgaki, M. Watarai et al. // *Biol.Pharm. Bull*. – 1999. – Vol. 22, No 10. – P. 1083-1088.